

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

Quantifying Links between Social Media and the Duration and Escalation of Violence During January 6th U.S. Capitol Insurrection

DATA

Our analysis uses the following data: (1) Parler videos recorded on Jan 6th, 2021 in Washington DC; (2) Tweets originally posted by Donald Trump on Jan 6th, 2021; (3) Tweets with hashtag *#stopthesteal* originally posted on Jan 6th, 2021; and (4) the Jan 6th Washington D.C. rally speeches. All data is publicly available per the links shown in Table S1.

Table S1: Data Sources

Variable	Coding Procedure	N	Data Source
Trump's tweets	Internet download and sampled in 5-minute intervals; Processed with python toolkit VADER.	16	https://www.thetrumparchive.com/
Violence level derived from Parler videos	Internet download and sampled in 5-minute intervals; Coded by research assistants.	17	https://projects.propublica.org/parler-capitol-videos/
Weapons level derived from Parler videos	Internet download and sampled in 5-minute intervals; Coded by research assistants.	38	https://projects.propublica.org/parler-capitol-videos/
#Stopthesteal tweets	Internet download and sampled in 5-minute intervals; These tweets were processed the same way as Trump's tweets.	7,550	https://twitter.com/ https://github.com/JustAnotherArchivist/snsrape
Rally Speeches	Internet download and sampled in 5-minute intervals; Authors manually counted the words and measured the length of cheers.	12	https://www.c-span.org/video/?507744-1/rally-electoral-college-vote-certification

PARLER VIDEO DATA

Sources of Videos: The Parler videos were uploaded and coded through a joint effort of several users and organizations, [1] which included a Twitter user (@donk_enby) [2], an Archive Team [3], and a volunteer collection of hackers and data researchers who archives the videos before Amazon Web Services stopped hosting Parler's website. In total, these websites posted 1113 recorded videos taken on Jan 6th, 2021.

Coding of Videos for Violence and Weapons: Coding was conducted by two trained research assistants. Each assistant watched and analyzed the Parler videos and coded each video by answering seven questions listed in Table 4 in the main text, and added a unique video ID and timestamp of when the video was taken.

154 videos were tagged for violence and weapons by video coders. The remaining videos contained footage of protestors walking, standing, marching, shouting, talking, or vandalizing –

events that can co-occur with violence but on their own are considered non-violent. Table S2 shows the details of the Washington, D.C. coding scheme and Figure S1 presents examples of still images and the coding of the identified violence or weaponry. In addition to using the Washington, D.C. coding scheme, we did robustness checks on the results using an alternative, popular coding scheme based on TV violence ratings(52). The results were nearly identical under both coding scheme (Table S7).

Trained assistants coded the January 6th videos for instances of violence and weaponry. The two assistants watched, analyzed, and then coded videos in response to seven questions. Table 4 in the Materials and Methods Section describes the questions and the details of the coding procedures. The interrater reliability score of the two coders was high to moderate with a Kappa of 90.63% and 90.28%, for violence and weaponry respectively.

Table S2 lists the criminal penalty for different violent acts or weapons vary according to D.C. statutes [4, 5], which provides an authoritative standard for quantifying the severity of a violent act and the lethality of weaponry through a point system. For example, the penalty associated with “weapons” is a “maximum fine of \$1000”. Given the fact that firearms are considered deadly or dangerous weapons, we assign 1500 to firearms and 1000 to clubs/bats/etc. for the violence and weaponry variables. Unconventional objects used as weapons, such as extinguishers, canes, flagpoles, were assigned the lowest value of 500.

Table S2: Coding scheme for Violence and weaponry levels using Statutory Guidelines

	Penalty	violation	reference
Weapons	up to \$1000	possession of unregistered firearm	"It is illegal to possess or sell a firearm in the Washington, DC without a valid registration certificate. The penalty for violating this section is a maximum fine of \$1000 and/or a maximum of one year imprisonment."
	up to \$1000	possession of a prohibited weapon (blackjack, sand club, switchblade, etc.)	"It is illegal to possess a whole range of “dangerous” weapons, including blackjack, sand club, switchblade, silencer or muffler, dagger, stiletto, or sawed off shotgun. It is also illegal to possess an imitation pistol, dagger, dirk, razor, stiletto or knife with a blade longer than three inches with the intent to use it unlawfully. The penalty for a first-time offender without a prior felony conviction is a maximum fine of \$1000 and/or up to a year incarceration."
	up to \$1000	unlawful possession of Ammunition	"It is also illegal to possess, sell or transfer any 'large capacity ammunition feeding device.' A person guilty of this charge can be sentenced to a maximum fine of \$1000 and/or up to a year imprisonment. D.C. Criminal Code 7-2506.01."
Violence	up to \$25000	aggravated assault attempted aggravated assault	"DC law states that aggravated assault occurs when a person purposefully causes serious bodily injury to another, or a person knowingly does something which creates a grave risk of serious bodily injury to another. Under circumstances that demonstrate an extreme indifference to human life" "Aggravated assault carries the penalty of a felony conviction, a fine of no more than \$25,000, up to 10 years in prison, or both. Attempted aggravated assault also carries serious penalties of a felony conviction, a fine of up to \$12,500, up to five years in prison, or both."
	up to \$1000	threats to do bodily harm	"The most minor of assault charges, Section 22-407 states that any person who threatens to do bodily harm to another person is guilty of misdemeanor assault. They face a fine of up to \$1000, up to six months in jail, or both."
	up to \$1000	assaulting an officer	"An individual convicted of assaulting an officer under these circumstances will be guilty of a misdemeanor and will face up to 180 days in jail, up to a \$1,000 fine, or both."

	up to \$25000	assaulting an officer	"By assaulting an officer and either harming the officer or creating a great risk of harm to the officer one faces much harsher penalties. This includes a felony conviction, as well as up to 10 years in prison, a \$25,000 fine, or both."
--	---------------	-----------------------	---

The value of violence level or weaponry level for each 5-minute interval is calculated by taking the maximum of the scores of all videos taken during that interval. The mean (standard deviation) of violence level is 116.319 (311.528), and of weaponry is 147.569 (398.072).

Figure S1 presents examples of the coding and operationalization of violence and weaponry variables in relation to snapshots taken from five different videos. The pie chart indicates what weapons coders to the website should tag in a video. Figure 2 shows the levels of violence and weapons for each five-minute interval starting at 9:00 to 18:00 hours.

Figure S1: Examples of Videos coded for Violence and Weaponry

Video ID:
ZhHAD9NO8kHg
Violence: Shoving
Violence level: 500
Responses: 1
Votes for "violence": 1

Video ID:
rKv1m3cDVn8K
Violence: Beating
Violence level: 1000
Total response: 2
Votes for "violence": 2

TRUMP TWEETS DATA DETAILS

Source of Tweets. Twitter permanently suspended Donald Trump’s account [6] on Jan. 8th, 2021 but his complete corpus of January 6th, 2021 Tweets were archived before being removed by Twitter and posted for public download at <https://www.thetrumparchive.com/> [7].

Coding of Tweets. We used the sentiment analysis toolkit VADER [8] to calculate the compound sentiment score in each tweet and multiplied it by the total length of each tweet) in each 5-minute interval from midnight to midnight on Jan 6th, 2021 to create a time series variables “sentiment strength” for our study.

Table S3 shows all of Trump’s tweets and their sentiment scores, number of likes and number of retweets. For example, at 9:00:12 AM Trump Tweeted, “They just happened to find 50,000 ballots late last night. The USA is embarrassed by fools. Our Election Process is worse than that of third world countries!” The negative sentiment score is 0.275, and the positive sentiment score is 0.

Table S3: Trump’s Tweets from Midnight to Midnight on 1/6/21

Time (EST)	Trump’s Tweets (Five retweets of other’s tweets are omitted here because they appear in #stopthesteel tweets).	Negative Sentiment	Neutral Sentiment	Positive Sentiment	Number of Likes	Number of Retweets
6:01:04 PM	These are the things and events that happen when a sacred landslide election victory is so unceremoniously & viciously stripped away from great patriots who have been badly & unfairly treated for so long. Go home with love & in peace. Remember this day forever!	0.098	0.693	0.209	0	0
3:13:26 PM	I am asking for everyone at the U.S. Capitol to remain peaceful. No violence! Remember, WE are the Party of Law & Order – respect the Law and our great men and women in Blue. Thank you!	0	0.614	0.386	730357	156100
2:38:58 PM	Please support our Capitol Police and Law Enforcement. They are truly on the side of our Country. Stay peaceful!	0	0.568	0.432	582183	107460
2:24:22 PM	Mike Pence didn’t have the courage to do what should have been done to protect our Country and our Constitution, giving States a chance to certify a corrected set of facts, not the fraudulent or inaccurate ones which they were asked to	0	0.731	0.269	0	0

	previously certify. USA demands the truth!					
10:44:31 AM	These scoundrels are only toying with the @sendavidperdue (a great guy) vote. Just didn't want to announce quite yet. They've got as many ballots as are necessary. Rigged Election!	0.073	0.76	0.166	246426	56883
9:16:30 AM	Even Mexico uses Voter I.D.	0	1	0	458141	72314
9:15:07 AM	The States want to redo their votes. They found out they voted on a FRAUD. Legislatures never approved. Let them do it. BE STRONG!	0.22	0.616	0.164	303347	69832
9:00:12 AM	They just happened to find 50,000 ballots late last night. The USA is embarrassed by fools. Our Election Process is worse than that of third world countries!	0.275	0.725	0	377295	92437
8:22:26 AM	THE REPUBLICAN PARTY AND, MORE IMPORTANTLY, OUR COUNTRY, NEEDS THE PRESIDENCY MORE THAN EVER BEFORE - THE POWER OF THE VETO. STAY STRONG!	0	0.629	0.371	344390	66595
8:17:22 AM	States want to correct their votes, which they now know were based on irregularities and fraud, plus corrupt process never received legislative approval. All Mike Pence has to do is send them back to the States, AND WE WIN. Do it Mike, this is a time for extreme courage!	0.106	0.734	0.16	251729	62503
8:06:45 AM	Sleepy Eyes Chuck Todd is so happy with the fake voter tabulation process that he can't even get the words out straight. Sad to watch!	0.182	0.615	0.203	193930	36209
1:00:50 AM	If Vice President @Mike_Pence comes through for us, we will win the Presidency. Many States want to decertify the mistake they made in certifying incorrect & even fraudulent numbers in a process	0.149	0.759	0.092	289835	66961

	NOT approved by their State Legislatures (which it must be). Mike can send it back!					
12:43:42 AM	Get smart Republicans. FIGHT! https://t.co/3fs1oPVnAx	0.389	0.322	0.29	127234	26083
12:08:24 AM	Just happened to have found another 4000 ballots from Fulton County. Here we go!	0	1	0	306738	69530
Row of means		0.880	0.779	0.133	277317	58631

GRANGER REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Wald Tests. The Wald test investigates the hypotheses that each of the other endogenous variables does not Granger-predict the dependent variable in that equation. Using a standard convention for reporting the regression results of Granger analysis, the column “**Equation**” represents the *Y* variable of the regression and the column “**Excluded**” represents the *X* variables of the regression.

Table S4: Granger Regressions and Wald tests

Equation (<i>Y</i> variable)	Excluded (<i>X</i> variables)	chi2	df	Prob > chi2
violence level	weaponry use level	5.1862	2	0.075
	Trump negative sentiment	2.9925	2	0.224
	Trump positive sentiment	7.0744	2	0.029
	cheers in warmup speeches	.56879	2	0.752
	cheers in Trump’s rally speech	39.762	2	0.000
	#sts positive sentiment	4.384	2	0.112
	#sts negative sentiment	17.034	2	0.000
	ALL	118	14	0.000
weaponry use level	violence level	8.3258	2	0.016
	Trump negative sentiment	1.9334	2	0.380
	Trump positive sentiment	7.7613	2	0.021
	cheers in warmup speeches	.33511	2	0.846
	cheers in Trump’s rally speech	23.732	2	0.000
	#sts positive sentiment	.74789	2	0.688
	#sts negative sentiment	14.326	2	0.001
	ALL	82.874	14	0.000
Trump negative sentiment	violence level	.12607	2	0.939
	weaponry use level	.96011	2	0.619
	Trump positive sentiment	.03388	2	0.983
	cheers in warmup speeches	.44463	2	0.801
	cheers in Trump’s rally speech	.05219	2	0.974
	#sts positive sentiment	.38443	2	0.825
	#sts negative sentiment	.03364	2	0.983
	ALL	2.4624	14	1.000
Trump positive sentiment	violence level	3.8721	2	0.144
	weaponry use level	1.4114	2	0.494
	Trump negative sentiment	.41353	2	0.813
	cheers in warmup speeches	1.3586	2	0.507
	cheers in Trump’s rally speech	.72678	2	0.695
	#sts positive sentiment	3.3501	2	0.187
	#sts negative sentiment	9.5099	2	0.009

	ALL	26.993	14	0.019
cheers in warmup speeches	violence level	.08984	2	0.956
	weaponry use level	.05829	2	0.971
	Trump negative sentiment	.24386	2	0.885
	Trump positive sentiment	.12684	2	0.939
	cheers in Trump's rally speech	.05063	2	0.975
	#sts positive sentiment	1.2905	2	0.525
	#sts negative sentiment	1.8079	2	0.405
	ALL	4.0358	14	0.995
cheers in Trump's rally speech	violence level	.44793	2	0.799
	weaponry use level	.21151	2	0.900
	Trump negative sentiment	.00967	2	0.995
	Trump positive sentiment	.15728	2	0.924
	cheers in warmup speeches	.06686	2	0.967
	#sts positive sentiment	2.8593	2	0.239
	#sts negative sentiment	.44654	2	0.800
	ALL	6.8066	14	0.942
#sts positive sentiment	violence level	1.7345	2	0.420
	weaponry use level	.13716	2	0.934
	Trump negative sentiment	2.7498	2	0.253
	Trump positive sentiment	.23752	2	0.888
	cheers in warmup speeches	1.0046	2	0.605
	cheers in Trump's rally speech	1.1079	2	0.575
	#sts negative sentiment	10.674	2	0.005
	ALL	25.57	14	0.029
#sts negative sentiment	violence level	3.4698	2	0.176
	weaponry use level	18.983	2	0.000
	Trump negative sentiment	2.6443	2	0.267
	Trump positive sentiment	5.128	2	0.077
	cheers in warmup speeches	.98296	2	0.612
	cheers in Trump's rally speech	3.4766	2	0.176
	#sts positive sentiment	12.023	2	0.002
	ALL	57.325	14	0.000

ROBUSTNESS CHECKS: GRANGER REGRESSIONS, VIOLENCE CODING SCHEME, AND SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Multivariate Granger Test in Matlab® Toolbox. To test whether the Granger relationships reported by the STATA Granger algorithm are method dependent, we ran Granger analyses using MVGC in Matlab Toolbox [9], which conducts numerical computation and statistical inference of Granger tests, conditional and unconditional, in both time and frequency domains. Although the p -values from the two different approaches may vary, the Granger causal connectivity agree to each other.

Table S5: Granger tests with MVGC Matlab® Toolbox:

Equation (Y variable)	Excluded (X variables)	df	Prob > chi2 (MVGC in Matlab)	Prob > chi2 (vargranger in Stata)
violence level	weaponry use level	2	0.110	0.075
	Trump negative sentiment	2	0.233	0.224
	Trump positive sentiment	2	0.041	0.029
	cheers in warmup speeches	2	0.756	0.752
	cheers in Trump's rally speech	2	0.000	0.000
	#sts positive sentiment	2	0.125	0.112
	#sts negative sentiment	2	0.001	0.000
	ALL	12		0.000
weaponry use level	violence level	2	0.025	0.016
	Trump negative sentiment	2	0.392	0.380
	Trump positive sentiment	2	0.029	0.021
	cheers in warmup speeches	2	0.848	0.846
	cheers in Trump's rally speech	2	0.000	0.000
	#sts positive sentiment	2	0.700	0.688
	#sts negative sentiment	2	0.003	0.001
	ALL	12		0.000
Trump negative sentiment	violence level	2	0.948	0.939
	weaponry use level	2	0.662	0.619
	Trump positive sentiment	2	0.984	0.983
	cheers in warmup speeches	2	0.803	0.801
	cheers in Trump's rally speech	2	0.974	0.974
	#sts positive sentiment	2	0.827	0.825
	#sts negative sentiment	2	0.987	0.983
	ALL	12		1.000
Trump positive sentiment	violence level	2	0.175	0.144
	weaponry use level	2	0.547	0.494
	Trump negative sentiment	2	0.815	0.813
	cheers in warmup speeches	2	0.512	0.507
	cheers in Trump's rally speech	2	0.696	0.695
	#sts positive sentiment	2	0.203	0.187

	#sts negative sentiment	2	0.012	0.009
	ALL	12		0.019
cheers in warmup speeches	violence level	2	0.960	0.956
	weaponry use level	2	0.975	0.971
	Trump negative sentiment	2	0.887	0.885
	Trump positive sentiment	2	0.941	0.939
	cheers in Trump's rally speech	2	0.975	0.975
	#sts positive sentiment	2	0.535	0.525
	#sts negative sentiment	2	0.495	0.405
	ALL	12		0.995
	cheers in Trump's rally speech	violence level	2	0.817
weaponry use level		2	0.913	0.900
Trump negative sentiment		2	0.995	0.995
Trump positive sentiment		2	0.927	0.924
cheers in warmup speeches		2	0.968	0.967
#sts positive sentiment		2	0.247	0.239
#sts negative sentiment		2	0.810	0.800
ALL		12		0.942
#sts positive sentiment	violence level	2	0.452	0.420
	weaponry use level	2	0.943	0.934
	Trump negative sentiment	2	0.259	0.253
	Trump positive sentiment	2	0.895	0.888
	cheers in warmup speeches	2	0.610	0.605
	cheers in Trump's rally speech	2	0.577	0.575
	#sts negative sentiment	2	0.012	0.005
	ALL	12		0.029
#sts negative sentiment	violence level	2	0.205	0.176
	weaponry use level	2	0.000	0.000
	Trump negative sentiment	2	0.273	0.267
	Trump positive sentiment	2	0.096	0.077
	cheers in warmup speeches	2	0.615	0.612
	cheers in Trump's rally speech	2	0.182	0.176
	#sts positive sentiment	2	0.003	0.002
	ALL	12		0.000

Alternative Coding Scheme. We conducted multiple Granger tests with alternative, popular coding scheme based on TV violence ratings [10] and summarized in Table S6:

Table S6. Robustness Check: Alternative coding scheme for violence level

Violence coding based on TV violence scale ⁴⁵	Violence coding based on D.C. criminal code ⁴⁴
1 = shooting	6 = shooting
3 = fist-fighting, pushing, striking	4 = pushing
4 = hitting with weapons/tools/knockout	3 = beating
6 = poisoning	1 = releasing smoke or tear gas

Granger tests were conducted with the following 4 combination of coding schemes.

A. *violence level* derived from DC status, *weaponry use level* derived from DC status, and all the other variables.

B. *violence level* derived from DC status, *weaponry use level* derived from TV violence scale, and all the other variables.

C. *violence level* derived from TV violence scale, *weaponry use level* derived from DC status, and all the other variables.

D. *violence level* derived from TV violence scale, *weaponry use level* derived from TV violence scale, and all the other variables.

The results were confirmatory, and the full regression are reported in Table S7:

Table S7. VAR results with different coding schemes.

Coding scheme		A	B	C	D
DV	IV	Coefficient			
violence level	L.violence level	0.26***	0.21**	0.39***	0.37***
	L2.violence level	-0.02	-0.06	0.06	0.03
	L.weaponry use level	0.07	0.14*	0.31	0.48
	L2.weaponry use level	0.10	0.20**	0.02	0.24
	L.Trump negative sentiment	-0.66	-0.66	-2.52	-2.56
	L2.Trump negative sentiment	0.24	0.19	-0.03	-0.06
	L.Trump positive sentiment	0.66*	0.69*	3.23**	3.40**
	L2.Trump positive sentiment	-0.36	-0.31	-0.55	-0.55
	L.cheers in warmup speeches	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.cheers in warmup speeches	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.cheers in Trump's rally speech	0.00***	0.00***	0.01***	0.01***
	L2.cheers in Trump's rally speech	-0.00**	-0.00**	-0.00***	-0.00***
	L.#sts positive sentiment	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.06
	L2.#sts positive sentiment	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
	L.#sts negative sentiment	-0.03	-0.03	-0.03	-0.03
	L2.#sts negative sentiment	0.08***	0.08***	0.31***	0.31***
	constant		-0.07**	-0.07**	-0.31**
	L.violence_level	0.15	0.13	0.03	0.04*

weaponry use level	L2.violence_level	0.16*	0.12	0.04*	0.03
	L.weaponry use level	0.03	-0.04	0.04	-0.06
	L2.weaponry use level	0.22**	0.24***	0.22***	0.22***
	L.Trump negative sentiment	-0.14	-0.19	-0.10	-0.16
	L2.Trump negative sentiment	-0.71	-0.65	-0.69	-0.61
	L.Trump positive sentiment	0.30	0.46	0.23	0.39
	L2.Trump positive sentiment	0.93**	0.95**	0.91*	0.89**
	L.cheers in warmup speeches	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.cheers in warmup speeches	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.cheers in Trump's rally speech	0.00***	0.00***	0.00***	0.00***
	L2.cheers in Trump's rally speech	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.#sts positive sentiment	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.#sts positive sentiment	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00
	L.#sts negative sentiment	-0.04	-0.01	-0.04	-0.01
	L2.#sts negative sentiment	0.09***	0.07***	0.09***	0.07***
	constant	-0.05	-0.06*	-0.05	-0.05*
Trump negative sentimentative	L.violence_level	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.violence_level	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.weaponry use level	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01
	L2.weaponry use level	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01
	L.Trump negative sentiment	-0.02	-0.01	-0.02	-0.01
	L2.Trump negative sentiment	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03
	L.Trump positive sentiment	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.02
	L2.Trump positive sentiment	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.01
	L.cheers in warmup speeches	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.cheers in warmup speeches	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.cheers in Trump's rally speech	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.cheers in Trump's rally speech	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.#sts positive sentiment	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.#sts positive sentiment	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.#sts negative sentiment	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.#sts negative sentiment	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
constant	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Trump positive sentimentative	L.violence_level	-0.03	-0.02	0.00	0.00
	L2.violence_level	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00
	L.weaponry use level	0.01	0.00	0.00	-0.01
	L2.weaponry use level	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.01
	L.Trump negative sentiment	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.05
	L2.Trump negative sentiment	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03
	L.Trump positive sentiment	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.03

	L2.Trump positive sentiment	-0.02	-0.01	-0.02	-0.02
	L.cheers in warmup speeches	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.cheers in warmup speeches	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.cheers in Trump's rally speech	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.cheers in Trump's rally speech	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.#sts positive sentiment	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.#sts positive sentiment	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
	L.#sts negative sentiment	-0.01**	-0.01*	-0.01**	-0.01**
	L2.#sts negative sentiment	0.01**	0.01**	0.01**	0.01**
	constant	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
cheers in warmup speeches	L.violence_level	-1.81	-1.89	-0.12	-0.11
	L2.violence_level	-1.63	-1.71	-0.13	-0.09
	L.weaponry use level	-0.82	-0.70	-1.55	-1.65
	L2.weaponry use level	-1.48	-1.68	-2.16	-2.70
	L.Trump negative sentiment	-23.96	-23.32	-24.71	-23.73
	L2.Trump negative sentiment	-12.81	-12.24	-12.51	-11.61
	L.Trump positive sentiment	-12.14	-12.99	-11.23	-12.60
	L2.Trump positive sentiment	-5.05	-5.63	-5.42	-6.28
	L.cheers in warmup speeches	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
	L2.cheers in warmup speeches	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
	L.cheers in Trump's rally speech	-0.01	-0.01	0.00	-0.01
	L2.cheers in Trump's rally speech	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01
	L.#sts positive sentiment	2.20	2.21	2.14	2.16
	L2.#sts positive sentiment	0.90	0.93	0.86	0.90
	L.#sts negative sentiment	0.86	0.81	0.88	0.81
L2.#sts negative sentiment	-3.30	-3.28	-3.33	-3.30	
constant	3.54	3.53	3.61	3.59	
cheers in Trump's rally speech	L.violence_level	-6.79	-5.44	-1.39	-1.10
	L2.violence_level	-6.85	-7.00	-1.08	-1.03
	L.weaponry use level	-3.51	-5.92	-4.17	-6.39
	L2.weaponry use level	-4.55	-5.24	-5.44	-6.48
	L.Trump negative sentiment	-4.55	-2.94	-6.85	-4.54
	L2.Trump negative sentiment	8.21	10.44	7.20	9.85
	L.Trump positive sentiment	-21.71	-24.17	-17.95	-21.26
	L2.Trump positive sentiment	-14.52	-16.38	-13.07	-15.59
	L.cheers in warmup speeches	-0.02	-0.02	-0.02	-0.02
	L2.cheers in warmup speeches	-0.02	-0.02	-0.02	-0.02
	L.cheers in Trump's rally speech	-0.02	-0.02	-0.02	-0.02
	L2.cheers in Trump's rally speech	0.00	0.00	-0.01	0.00
L.#sts positive sentiment	6.71	6.79	6.52	6.61	

	L2.#sts positive sentiment	0.32	0.40	0.27	0.37
	L.#sts negative sentiment	3.14	2.93	3.18	2.95
	L2.#sts negative sentiment	-1.60	-1.39	-1.45	-1.30
	constant	-5.80	-5.95	-5.84	-5.95
#sts positive sentimentitive	L.violence_level	0.25	0.28	-0.02	-0.01
	L2.violence_level	0.14	0.11	0.06	0.05
	L.weaponry use level	0.06	0.01	0.18	0.16
	L2.weaponry use level	0.03	0.10	0.02	0.11
	L.Trump negative sentiment	-1.95	-1.98	-1.93	-2.00
	L2.Trump negative sentiment	-1.47	-1.46	-1.59	-1.59
	L.Trump positive sentiment	0.47	0.52	0.45	0.56
	L2.Trump positive sentiment	-0.08	-0.09	0.05	0.03
	L.cheers in warmup speeches	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.cheers in warmup speeches	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.cheers in Trump's rally speech	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.cheers in Trump's rally speech	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.#sts positive sentiment	0.25***	0.25***	0.25***	0.25***
	L2.#sts positive sentiment	0.25***	0.25***	0.25***	0.25***
	L.#sts negative sentiment	0.21**	0.21**	0.22**	0.22**
	L2.#sts negative sentiment	-0.02	-0.02	-0.02	-0.02
	constant	0.36***	0.36***	0.35***	0.36***
#sts negative sentimentative	L.violence_level	-0.37	-0.27	-0.12**	-0.11*
	L2.violence_level	0.03	0.12	0.03	0.03
	L.weaponry use level	0.55***	0.46*	0.60***	0.56**
	L2.weaponry use level	0.40*	0.39*	0.42**	0.46*
	L.Trump negative sentiment	-1.80	-2.17	-1.89	-2.24
	L2.Trump negative sentiment	-0.92	-1.04	-0.98	-1.13
	L.Trump positive sentiment	1.71*	2.15*	1.82*	2.24**
	L2.Trump positive sentiment	-0.80	-0.73	-0.66	-0.57
	L.cheers in warmup speeches	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.cheers in warmup speeches	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.cheers in Trump's rally speech	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L2.cheers in Trump's rally speech	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	L.#sts positive sentiment	0.13*	0.12*	0.12*	0.12*
	L2.#sts positive sentiment	0.10	0.09	0.10	0.09
	L.#sts negative sentiment	0.36***	0.38***	0.36***	0.38***
	L2.#sts negative sentiment	0.24***	0.23***	0.25***	0.24***
	constant	0.20**	0.21**	0.19**	0.20**

Sensitivity Analysis. To address the possible sampling limitations in video data, we conducted several computational tests typical in the literature on extremism to gauge how robust the results are to measurement error (3, 36) . Our tests showed that the results are robust to measurement error and sampling bias.

First, to gauge the stability of our findings to random measurement error, we randomly removed 5% of the videos and reran our analyses on the randomly reduced set of videos and then compared the significant levels of the full sample findings to the reduced sample findings. We conducted this test 200 separate times, keeping track of the fraction of times the reported (full sample) findings were statistically significant in the reduced sample. Once our fraction was computed, we conducted a binomial test. The binomial test has k trials set to 200 and n success set to the number of times the reduced sample analysis produced a statistically significant result for a particular variable in our analysis (e.g., the relationship between former President Trump’s tweeting and increases, decreases, or no change in the level of violence). Our model had six statistically significant regression coefficients and all six remained statistically significant according to the binomial tests, indicating that the results are unlikely to have occurred by chance. Similarly, all the variables that were non-significant in our model, remained non-significant according to the binomial test.

Second, the above test was conducted again but in the opposite direction. This time we added 5% more violence to the video at random to detect whether adding mismeasured violence would change the reported results. Again, these tests indicated that the reported results are unlikely to be due to measurement error in the coding of the videos.

Table S8. Sensitivity analysis: Granger test results with 5% error introduction

Equation (<i>Y</i> variable)	Excluded (<i>X</i> variables)	Original result Prob > chi2	Robustness check: percentage of <i>p</i> -value < 0.05 (100 trials for each case)	
			With randomly reduced violence	With randomly increased violence
violence level	weaponry use level	0.072	14%	11%
	Trump negative sentiment	0.223	0%	0%
	Trump positive sentiment	0.034	78%	79%
	cheers in warmup speeches	0.771	0%	0%
	cheers in Trump’s speech	0.000	99%	100%
	#sts positive sentiment	0.119	7%	5%
	#sts negative sentiment	0.002	100%	100%
weaponry use level	violence level	0.012	83%	87%
	Trump negative sentiment	0.280	0%	0%
	Trump positive sentiment	0.006	93%	92%
	cheers in warmup speeches	0.857	0%	0%
	cheers in Trump’s speech	0.000	91%	93%
	#sts positive sentiment	0.698	0%	0%
	#sts negative sentiment	0.011	100%	100%
Trump negative sentiment	violence level	0.940	0%	0%
	weaponry use level	0.633	0%	0%
	Trump positive sentiment	0.970	0%	0%
	cheers in warmup speeches	0.805	0%	0%
	cheers in Trump’s speech	0.972	0%	0%
	#sts positive sentiment	0.812	0%	0%
	#sts negative sentiment	0.990	0%	0%
Trump positive sentiment	violence level	0.173	0%	0%
	weaponry use level	0.528	0%	0%
	Trump negative sentiment	0.831	0%	0%

	cheers in warmup speeches	0.509	0%	0%
	cheers in Trump's speech	0.702	0%	0%
	#sts positive sentiment	0.224	0%	0%
	#sts negative sentiment	0.013	100%	100%
cheers in warmup speeches	violence level	0.971	0%	0%
	weaponry use level	0.961	0%	0%
	Trump negative sentiment	0.887	0%	0%
	Trump positive sentiment	0.937	0%	0%
	cheers in Trump's speech	0.976	0%	0%
	#sts positive sentiment	0.527	0%	0%
	#sts negative sentiment	0.498	0%	0%
	cheers in Trump's speech	violence level	0.838	0%
weaponry use level		0.879	0%	0%
Trump negative sentiment		0.994	0%	0%
Trump positive sentiment		0.918	0%	0%
cheers in warmup speeches		0.966	0%	0%
#sts positive sentiment		0.236	0%	0%
#sts negative sentiment		0.814	0%	0%
#sts positive sentiment	violence level	0.440	0%	0%
	weaponry use level	0.888	0%	0%
	Trump negative sentiment	0.262	0%	0%
	Trump positive sentiment	0.889	0%	0%
	cheers in warmup speeches	0.608	0%	0%
	cheers in Trump's speech	0.582	0%	0%
#sts negative sentiment	#sts negative sentiment	0.014	100%	100%
	violence level	0.179	0%	0%
	weaponry use level	0.000	100%	100%
	Trump negative sentiment	0.204	0%	0%
	Trump positive sentiment	0.057	2%	1%
	cheers in warmup speeches	0.615	0%	0%
	cheers in Trump's speech	0.186	0%	0%
	#sts positive sentiment	0.006	100%	100%

References

- [1] The Hacker Who Archived Parler Explains How She Did It (and What Comes Next), <https://www.vice.com/en/article/n7vqew/the-hacker-who-archived-parler-explains-how-she-did-it-and-what-comes-next>
- [2] Twitter user @donk_enby https://twitter.com/donk_enby?lang=en
- [3] Twitter user Archive Team <https://twitter.com/archiveteam?lang=en>
- [4] Penalty on firearms/weapons <https://koehlerlaw.net/criminal-defense-dc/weapons/>
- [5] DC Assault Laws <https://criminallawdc.com/dc-assault-lawyer/laws/>
- [6] Twitter Inc., Permanent suspension of @realDonaldTrump, Jan. 8th, 2021, https://blog.twitter.com/en_us/topics/company/2020/suspension.html
- [7] Trump Twitter Archive, <https://www.thetrumparchive.com/>
- [8] Hutto, C.J. & Gilbert, E.E. (2014). VADER: A Parsimonious Rule-based Model for Sentiment Analysis of Social Media Text. Eighth International Conference on Weblogs and Social Media (ICWSM-14). Ann Arbor, MI, June 2014.
- [9] L. Barnett and A. K. Seth, The MVGC Multivariate Granger Causality Toolbox: A New Approach to Granger-causal Inference, J. Neurosci. Methods 223, 2014.
- [10] Mustonen A, Pulkkinen L. Television violence: A development of a coding scheme[J]. Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media, 1997, 41(2): 168-189.